

Coping Practices and Academic Attitudes of Maritime Students in the Philippines

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ABSTRACT

The recognized role of coping practices in shaping students' academic behaviors has raised increasing attention regarding their impact on academic attitudes among maritime students. The primary goal of this study was to determine how coping practices influence academic attitudes among Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation (BSMT) students at DMMA College of Southern Philippines, Inc. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational approach was used. The study was conducted in Davao City, Philippines, with 335 BSMT students as participants, selected through simple random sampling. The data were collected using a modified survey questionnaire measuring coping practices along two domains emotion-focused and problem-

focused and academic attitudes across three indicators: attitude towards teachers, attitude towards other students, and attitude towards how classes are handled. Data were analyzed using statistical methods, including mean and standard deviation, Pearson's r , and multiple regression. The results revealed that students show a high level of coping practices, with emotion-focused coping slightly higher than problem-focused coping. Similarly, students exhibited a high level of academic attitudes across all three indicators, with attitudes toward teachers obtaining the highest mean rating, this suggests that students particularly value the role their teachers play in their overall learning experience. Pearson's correlation analysis revealed a statistically significant, moderate positive relationship between coping practices and academic attitudes, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis. Furthermore, regression analysis confirmed that both emotion-focused and problem-focused coping are significant predictors of academic attitudes, with problem-focused coping emerging as the stronger predictor. These findings suggest that effective coping practices positively influence students' academic attitudes when used consistently and adaptively. Purposeful use of coping strategies promotes favorable academic dispositions among maritime students. It is recommended that students continually develop adaptive coping skills. Schools should integrate coping programs into their student support services. Future researchers should explore additional variables and broader contexts to further confirm these findings.

Keywords: *Coping Practices, Academic Attitudes, Maritime Students, and Davao City*

INTRODUCTION

Students' negative academic attitudes have been a major problem affecting education worldwide and, in turn, the way they process and respond to information Govorova E, Benítez I and Muñoz J (2020). Such an affective state must be considered as students' cognitive, affective, and behavioral aspects play an important role in their academic outcomes (Perloff, 2016; Nja et al., 2022). Recent research indicates that perceiving the learning environment as adverse fosters negative attitudes that hinder both performance and sustained engagement (Nja et al., 2022). These attitudes often stem from students' expectations and the actual school environment, resulting in decreased motivation and a higher risk of dropout.

In Israel, a persistent issue confronting education system is the gap between positive school environments and students' academic performance, especially in technical and core subject areas. Recent research shows that the relationship between teachers and students, along with teachers' emotional characteristics, strongly influences students' school experiences and attitudes, yet these connections alone do not automatically lead to improved school performance outcomes (Nulman & Alkalay, 2023). Many studies from different countries show that students generally feel positive about their school environment, teacher support, and overall school experience, these positive feelings do not always lead to high academic performance. This suggests that global education policies may sometimes place too much emphasis on student well-being without giving equal attention to the quality of instruction and how well the curriculum is designed and aligned (Florida, 2025). This concern is also evident in how values, education, and teacher-related factors are incorporated into classroom instruction. Despite their significance for students' personal and overall development, these factors remain unnoticed and understudied. Gálvez-Nieto et al. (2022) argue that students' character can be developed through values, just as their academic performance can be influenced by other factors, but they add that values play a marginal role, if any, in academic achievement. On the other hand, a positive and supportive school climate can foster responsible, caring, and socially conscious students, but it is not a guarantee of improved academic performance. Overall, the results underscore this global educational problem. Schools are already providing students with a safe and supportive environment that enables their social development, yet this very advantage still becomes a barrier to their academic success. This clearly shows the need for educational reforms that effectively motivate students while ensuring they achieve high academic standards through well-designed teaching methods and educational goals (Nulmana & Alkalay, 2023).

In the Philippines, students are faced with significant challenges that profoundly shape how they manage their responsibilities and shape their overall attitude towards learning. This mindset is not a reflection of their personality it is a factor in determining a student's long-term success. According to Del Rosario & Kitada (2020), developing effective practices maintain a positive academic position, it is essential for navigating the hardships of education. Students utilize various methods to sustain their motivation, commitment to their studies, ranging from proactive problem-solving. Honra (2022) notes that by utilizing connections with friends and family, students are better able to maintain a productive outlook on education, even when facing academic setbacks. Ansong et al. (2023) suggest that these approaches are vital for fostering and maintaining a persistent, growth-oriented mindset. Ultimately, the effectiveness of these coping practices whether practical or emotional serves as a motivation for academic attitude. As Plaza, A. E. C. (2023) emphasizes, the ability to maintain a character is a make-or-break factor for progression in maritime education.

In Davao City and its neighboring provinces, there is cognitive overload that affects their attitudes toward learning or school pressure. This is associated with negative consequences that adversely affect students' mental health and school performance, but can be alleviated significantly through efficient coping responses. Culanag et al. (2025) found that these stressors create unfavorable conditions that diminish students' motivation, focus, and overall well-being. However, the study also demonstrated that when students develop strong psychological well-being through positive thinking, social support, and adaptive coping they are significantly better equipped to manage environmental pressures, resulting in higher

academic performance despite the presence of stressors (Dulay et al., 2023). This highlights the need for institutions to respond agilely to address student emotional exhaustion (Bakker et al., 2024). Knowing how to handle the pressures of demanding coursework and career expectations is crucial for long-term success and mental well-being.

Despite other research studies establishing coping and academic attitudes among students, a specific study on maritime students' coping practices and attitudes toward school-related factors remains unexplored. Plaza, A. E. C. (2023) found that coping practices among maritime students in the Philippines employ both emotion-focused and problem-focused strategies to handle academic challenges; however, this literature was limited to online class learning and did not explore students' attitudes toward school-related factors in relation to their coping behaviours in traditional, face-to-face education. On the other hand, Peña and Empic (2023) stated that social support and coping mechanisms for mental stress among maritime students led to higher levels of coping with school factors, including learning performance, but this study did not delve into students' attitudes toward specific school factors. In contrast, Florida (2025) found no significant relationship between maritime students' attitudes towards school-related factors and their academic performance. This article did not assess and include coping practices, which limits the information regarding how attitudes and coping contribute to student performance. Therefore, despite evidence highlighting the importance of coping mechanisms for academic success, there is a distinct gap in quantitative research linking coping practices with attitudes toward school-related factors, specifically among maritime students in the Philippines, underscoring the need for the present study at DMMA College of Southern Philippines.

In this study, coping practices refer to the cognitive and behavioural strategies students use to manage stress and challenges related to their learning, while attitudes toward school-related factors refer to students' overall perceptions and feelings about their academic environment, tasks, and responsibilities at university. Research in educational psychology suggests that students' coping strategies are linked to attitudes and responses to academic stress and educational demands, indicating that coping approaches can influence students' educational outcomes and attitudes toward learning environments (He, 2023). In addition, adaptive coping strategies such as positive reappraisal and planning are instrumental in moderating students' stress responses, which in turn can affect their engagement and disposition toward academic tasks (Ruiz-Camacho et al., 2025). Lastly, effective coping strategies are associated with higher academic satisfaction, suggesting that students' coping styles can influence their attitudes toward school-related factors, especially in learning experiences (Barbé et al., 2025). These findings suggest that coping practices really affect and link students' attitudes in educational contexts. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the coping practices related to attitudes toward school-related factors among maritime students at DMMA College of Southern Philippines.

The findings of this study will be disseminated to the school research associates to ensure that the results contribute to school development and students' learning responses. The research outcomes will be presented to the DMMA College of Southern Philippines administration, faculty members, and maritime students through an institutional research presentation. The result of this study will be submitted to the college library for future reference. Through these dissemination methods, the study aims to inform and improve policy formulation, enhance student support programs, and contribute to the existing strategies on coping practices and attitudes toward school-related factors among maritime students.

Statement of the Problem

This study will determine the Coping practices and academic attitudes among marine transportation students at a maritime institution in Davao City, Philippines during the second semester, S.Y 2025-2026.

1. What is the level of students' coping mechanism in terms of:
 - 1.1. Emotion-focused; and,

- 1.2. Problem-focused?
2. What is the level of students' academic attitudes in terms of:
 - 2.1. Attitude towards teacher;
 - 2.2. Attitude towards other students; and,
 - 2.3. Attitude towards how classes are handled?
3. Is there a significant relationship between coping mechanism and academic attitudes and
4. What domains of coping mechanism significantly influences academic attitudes of the maritime students?

Literature Review

This section discusses the literature related to the study. The information is displayed according to the study's variables: coping practices and academic attitudes. Plaza, A. E. C. (2023), claimed that coping practices have the following indicators: emotion-focused and problem-focused. Atienza et al. (2017) asserted that academic attitudes include attitudes toward teachers, other students, classroom management, instructional materials, and facilities.

Coping Practices

In this research, it refers to conscious, intentional, and dynamic cognitive or behavioral efforts used to manage internal and external stressful situations that are appraised as taxing or exceeding one's resources. It means that coping practices are thoughts and behaviors mobilized to manage stress. Supporting this definition, Plaza, A. E. C. (2023) explained that coping practices are techniques people use to better manage unpleasant or challenging emotions when they are stressed or traumatized, or when they feel helpless, frustrated, and overwhelmed in class.

Emotion-Focused

Algorani and Gupta (2020) asserted that coping practices encompass denial, acceptance, seeking religious support, positive reinterpretation, and emotional support, all of which help individuals manage discomforting issues. Furthermore, Waterhouse P. and Samra, R. (2026) states that not all students have the exact coping practices to facilitate their emotional well-being in times of uncertainty. There are so many coping strategies that students can adopt. Therefore, coping practices affect the students' attitudes towards school-related factors. The research conducted by Nadarajan, S., et al. (2023) found that maritime students use connectivity and digital distractions to manage their emotions. Maritime students use the internet and social media for things they enjoy, like watching videos and memes, and also to stay in touch with their friends and family. This is how maritime students cope with feeling stressed and tired, so they do not get overwhelmed. Maritime students use media and the internet to have some fun and relax, which helps them avoid burnout.

Problem-Focused

Algorani and Gupta (2020) asserted that coping practices include engaging in active actions, suspending competitive activities, suspending coping behaviors, and seeking social support. That further aims to lessen the negative feelings associated with the effects. In addition, Liu, X., et al. (2024) emphasize that engaging in active problem-solving activities can lead to direct stressors. As a result, students become more confident and self-controlled by focusing on concrete measures that enhance their abilities. Acquiring problem-focused strategies is far from merely being self-reliant. It also involves reaching out to others and preparing yourself with the right help and resources. For maritime students, this usually involves speaking with the officers and teachers whenever they encounter difficulties. Research by Karahalil et al. (2025) highlighted the importance of this kind of "help" in supporting students in closing the gap between classroom lessons and real-life on-board tasks. They rely on guidance and mentorship to easily understand

how to apply what they have learned in practical situations. The study itself also points out that consistently participating in simulation-based training is another tool for coping with problems. By repeatedly practicing emergency procedures to build their own confidence. What feels stressful or intimidating becomes Manageable through practice, making their fear of future onboarding responsibilities less intense.

Academic attitudes

Students' attitudes toward academic factors reflect their views of teachers, classmates, and class management; these views determine their learning efforts. A positive attitude thus fosters a strong mind that can withstand and continue learning, while a negative one leads to a lack of motivation and to giving up. It is through their interpretations and reactions to their total school experience that students determine their academic performance (Atienza et al., 2017).

Attitude towards Teacher

Wubbels, T., and Brekelmans, M. (2005) pointed out that one of the primary factors that determines the formation of these attitudes is the quality of communication and the student-teacher relationship. On the one hand, positive interactions between the two parties foster the development of ethical values and a sense of respect. On the other hand, if one party exercises authority excessively, the other party tends to adopt a critical or disrespectful stance. Between the two parties foster the development of ethical values and a sense of respect. On the other hand, if one party exercises authority excessively, the other party tends to adopt a critical or disrespectful stance.

The same idea was expressed by Tian and Shen (2023), who argued that a teacher's conduct has a considerable impact on students' motivation. Among various external factors influencing students' academic learning, the role of teachers cannot be underestimated. Students can quickly lose motivation when teachers come across as discouraging. On the other hand, students feel more valued or appreciated when their teachers are enthusiastic, supportive, and encouraging. Al-Shumaimeri, Y. (2024) found a strong correlation between students' courage, interest, and supportive teacher attitudes. This is to say that if teachers are genuinely passionate about their subject and provide students with a positive, meaningful critique, students will not only learn the subject with pleasure but will also develop a positive attitude towards both the subject and the teachers. This supports the findings of Erginer et al. (2023), who noted that when students perceive a teacher as uninterested or ineffective, their own interest in the subject tends to decline, this lack of interest can lead to reduced lower motivation.

Attitude towards other Students'

Knickenberg, M., and Zubriggen (2025) and Shao Y et al. (2024) discovered that students perform better academically when they sense support from their classmates and feel a sense of inclusion. Peer support helps students feel a sense of belonging in school, encouraging them to learn more and persist even when challenges arise. The individuals they attend school with turn into more than just classmates. They form friendships that help them manage the pressures of school and the challenging tasks they face. (Worley, J.T., et al., 2023). When students perceive they lack friends or experience unkindness from classmates, it can lead to a dislike for school. According to Fragata L. et al. (2023), a student's motivation to study can be heavily influenced by their classmates' behavior and opinions. It is mainly when the school is regarded as unimportant by a large number of students that the rest gradually come to share the same view. In addition, experiences such as loneliness or bullying can negatively affect a student's emotions and reduce their willingness to complete school tasks. Plys and Desrichard (2020) found that students who feel lonely often experience stress and fatigue, which makes it harder for them to focus on their studies. Also, these moods can make students angry or frustrated in school. These kinds of effects are not limited to face, to, face settings only. Bakker et al. (2024) argued that unpleasant encounters with peers online might lead to anxiety, and the student may become unwilling to go to school physically, thus resulting in lower enjoyment and satisfaction with the learning environment.

Attitude towards how classes are handled

Florida, A. H. (2025), stated that students from the sampled schools generally have a positive image of the facilities and learning materials, but their views on classroom management and teacher involvement better reflect their overall satisfaction with the schools. This also illustrates the extent of the students' academic and emotional adjustment to the educational system. Attitude reflects the actual "handling" of their classes, including teaching methods and the teacher's ability to manage the learning environment. This attitude serves as a dependent variable and is frequently conceptualized using the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) developed by Ajzen Icek (2020).

According to Qiu (2022), a lack of effective classroom management strategies often results in a chaotic environment that hinders students from reaching their full potential and negatively impacts their behavioral intentions. Furthermore, Nisar, Khan, and Khan (2019) note that students' reactions to lessons are heavily influenced by the teacher's ability to maintain discipline and utilize contemporary, learner-centered teaching methods.

Theoretical Framework

In this study, the two theories will be the primary use of the study of coping practices and academic attitudes. Biggs, A., et al (2017) Lazarus and Folkman's Transactional Model of Stress and Coping Theory, and Ryan and Deci's Self-Determination Theory (2020). The Transactional Model of Stress and Coping suggest that students' responses to academic pressure are determined by their cognitive appraisal of school-related factors as manageable demand or excessive pressures, which dictates their choice of adaptive or maladaptive coping practices. This method is influenced by Self-Determination Theory, which suggests that when schools foster independence, competence, and connectedness, students will lean more on positive attitude and use proactive coping practices, the combined effect of these theories is that effective coping practices are observed when students see themselves as good individuals within a supportive educational framework that meets their emotional needs. Florida A. H. (2025) suggests that students' attitudes toward academic attitudes, such as workload and availability of learning resources, significantly shape their choice of coping practices. When students perceive these factors as "taxing" or exceeding their personal resources, they often experience academic burnout, characterized by emotional depletion and a decline in academic self-efficacy (He, J. 2023). Therefore, students who maintain a negative attitude or feel overwhelmed by sustained pressure are more likely to employ avoidant coping strategies or manifest behavioral disengagement, such as procrastination (Bittmann, F. (2021).

On the other hand, Self-Determination Theory (SDT) emphasizes that school environments that support basic psychological needs foster more adaptive coping capacities and positive academic attitudes (Ryan & Deci, 2020). Liu et al. (2024) reported that students who experience high levels of learning satisfaction and engagement tend to view school-related challenges as manageable, leading them to use constructive, problem-focused coping practices such as active planning and seeking social support. In addition, academic resilience plays a very important role; students with greater adaptability can recover from challenges by drawing on their own strengths and external teacher support to maintain or secure a positive attitude toward their academics (Bittmann, 2021). This angle shows that a positive school environment and available social support are crucial for reducing stress and encouraging students to cope in active, healthy ways (Zuhriyah et al. 2023).

Conceptual Framework

Shown in Figure 1, the key variables of the study are presented. Coping practices are considered a key factor affecting results, as defined by Plaza, A. E. C. (2023), and refer to the ways students act and think in response to stress or challenges in the school environment. Coping practices manages emotions and actively addresses challenges, enabling students to handle stress, workloads, and demands. The dependent variable in this study is academic attitudes, which refers to their feelings, thoughts, and behaviors in response to diverse challenges within the school environment. According to Atienza et al. (2017), these

attitudes influence students' reactions to teachers, classmates, and the organization and conduct of their classes.

Figure 1. *Conceptual Framework of the Study*

In this study, the researchers examine students' academic attitudes, including their teachers, classmates, and classroom behavior. The study also examines students' coping practices, specifically emotion-focused and problem-focused coping. It is based on the idea that the way maritime students handle stress and challenges can influence how they see and experience school. When students use ineffective coping strategies, they may develop negative views about their school environment. On the other hand, when they use effective coping strategies, they are more likely to have positive attitudes toward their teachers, peers, and classroom experiences.

METHODS

This chapter presents the method to be employed to analyze the data in this study, including the research design, research location, research respondents, research instrument, data-gathering procedures, and statistical analysis.

Research Design

This study will utilize a descriptive correlational research design to investigate the relationship between students' coping practices and their attitudes toward school-related factors. Pulmano, R. A., et al. (2024) stated that the quantitative method is best suited for identifying people's approaches to managing stress and for determining whether these approaches affect how students view the learning environment. Data will be collected through the distribution of a personal survey to obtain a stratified sample of maritime students. The researchers will then evaluate the strength of the relationship between the variables using Pearson's r and multiple regression to provide a statistical foundation.

Research Locale

This quantitative, non-experimental study will be conducted in one of the well-known educational institutes in Davao City. The study will be carried out at DMMA College of the Southern Philippines, Inc., one of the top maritime schools in Davao City. The researchers aim to examine the significance of coping practices as a driver of student performance by focusing on location and student group within the BSMT. This is to better understand the dynamics unfolding in a maritime academic setting; the main goal is to assess the relationship between the IV (coping practices) and the DV (attitudes toward school-related factors).

Participants and Sampling Technique

The respondents in the study were BSMT students from first to third year enrolled at DMMA College of the Southern Philippines during the academic year 2025-2026. These groups were selected to examine the coping practices and attitudes towards school-related factors across different academic stages. The total population of eligible BSMT students was 2,049, distributed as follows: 689 in the first year, 681 in the second year: 679; and 679 in the third year. The researchers used Slovin’s formula with a 0.05 confidence level was used to determine the sample size, yielding a sample of 335 respondents. The sample was proportionally distributed as follows: 113 from the first year, 111 from the second year, and 111 from the third year. Simple random sampling was used to select participants, minimizing bias. Feasibility considerations included costs, facilities, time, and personnel. Ethical approval from the DMMA College Institutional Review Board ensured informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation.

Research Instrument

The researchers will use a descriptive-correlational survey design, with questionnaires adapted from Plaza, A. E. C. (2023) and Atienza et al. (2017), to examine the coping practices of maritime students and their attitudes toward school-related factors. Some research questions will be retained, while others will be revised after thorough reading of books, theses, journals, and other related studies relevant to the present research. The two-part questionnaire will be submitted to a panel of experts for approval and validation to ensure its content validity. After validation, the instrument will undergo pilot testing among selected maritime students who will not be included as actual respondents in the study. The instrument's reliability will be assessed using Cronbach’s Alpha to evaluate its internal consistency. Necessary revisions, polishing, and refinement of the questionnaire will be made based on the results of the validation and pilot testing. The survey questionnaire will contain two parts for the respondents to answer. The first part will aim to determine students’ Coping Practices. It will consist of twenty-two (22) items unevenly distributed into two indicators — Emotion-Focused Coping (13 items) and Problem-Focused Coping (9 items). The five orderable gradations of coping practices with their respective range of means and interpretations will be as follows:

Range of Means Descriptive Level		Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	Coping practices will always be observed
3.40 – 4.19	High	Coping practices will oftentimes be observed
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	Coping practices will sometimes be observed
1.80 – 2.59	Low	Coping practices will seldom be observed
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Coping practices will not be observed

The second part will aim to measure students’ academic attitudes. It will consist of nineteen (19) items unevenly distributed into three indicators: Attitude toward Teacher (10 items), Attitude toward Other Students (5 items), and Attitude toward How Classes are Handled (4 items). For this variable, the respondents will answer the given statements based on the following five orderable gradations with their respective range of means and interpretations:

Range of Means Descriptive Level		Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	Positive attitudes will always be manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	High	Positive attitudes will oftentimes be manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	Positive attitudes will sometimes be manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Low	Positive attitudes will seldom be manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Positive attitudes will not be manifested

Data Gathering

The data were gathered through an organized and systematic process. First, the researchers requested permission to conduct the study by sending a letter, signed by their adviser, to the Office of the Dean of the Maritime Department. The letter was approved after four working days. After approval, a copy of the endorsed letter was sent to the college instructors to formally inform them and allow the researchers to carry out the study. Before the researchers distributed the questionnaires, the researchers coordinated with the Office of the College Registrar to obtain the official list of the first-year to third-year Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation (BSMT) students enrolled in the second semester of School Year 2025–2026. The list is used to determine the total number of maritime students. The researchers then used simple random sampling with Slovin's formula to determine the number of respondents. Before the survey, consent forms were provided and discussed to guarantee voluntary participation and that Students were aware of the study's objectives. The researchers themselves distributed and explained the questionnaires to the chosen participants. Clear instructions were provided to help the respondents answer properly. After completion, the researchers personally collected the questionnaires. Then the questionnaires were collected, the data were checked, tallied, and organized for analysis. The results were then tabulated and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools, with assistance from a statistician.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used in analyzing the data gathered in this study. The **Mean** served as the main measure of central tendency, providing the average values of the variables under investigation. This tool was utilized to address the first and second research questions. **Pearson r** was employed to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the two variables and was used to respond to the third research question. Lastly, **Regression Analysis** was applied to examine how one variable depends on another by establishing a linear equation that best fits the observed data, which was used to address the fourth research question of this study.

Ethical Consideration

This study followed ethical standards to protect all participants involved. Before the study began, the researchers sent a formal request letter to the administration of DMMA College of Southern Philippines and waited for approval before collecting data. The researchers also coordinated with the Maritime Department and the relevant faculty members to make sure the study was properly conducted. The participants, who were Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation (BSMT) students, were informed about what the study was about, how it would be conducted, and why it was important. Joining the study was optional, and all participants gave their consent before the survey questionnaires were given out.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter outlines the results and analysis of the survey data, coping practices, and Academic Attitudes among BSMT students at DMMA College of Southern Philippines. The discussions are sequenced according to the following subheadings: level of students' Coping practices, level of students' academic attitudes, relationship between coping practices and students' academic attitudes, and regression analysis of coping practices and Academic attitudes.

Level of Students' Coping Practices

A total of 335 maritime students fit the inclusion criteria. Table 1 shows the level of coping practices. It has an overall mean of 3.92, which is described as high. This means that a standard deviation below 1.0 indicates that their responses are the same.

Table 1. *Level of Coping Practices*

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Emotion-Focused	0.61	3.94	High
Problem-Focused	0.72	3.89	High
Total	0.61	3.92	

The high level of Coping Practices indicates that they are observed at all times. This suggests that the respondents frequently employ effective methods to manage stress and challenges in their academic environment. There was little variation in how the students evaluated and used their coping practices, as indicated by a standard deviation of less than 1.0, suggesting consistency among the respondents. When categorized, Emotion-Focused obtained a category mean of 3.94 (SD=0.61), which is also considered high. Certain items in this category demonstrated a high degree of agreement; some even attained a “Very High” level of coping practices. In contrast, Problem-Focused yielded a mean of 3.89 (SD=0.72), which is also considered high. This suggests that the students are equally skilled at managing their emotional responses and actively addressing the underlying causes of their issues.

According to Lazarus and Folkman's (1984) theoretical framework, coping is defined as continuously shifting cognitive and behavioral efforts to manage particular external and/or internal demands that are evaluated as taxing or exceeding the person's resources. This finding is consistent with the finding that maritime students exhibit a high level of coping practices. The high mean scores indicate that the students have the coping mechanisms necessary to meet the demands of maritime education. The high frequency of emotion-focused practices suggests that students can control their emotions in the face of academic pressures. According to Schoenmakers et al. (2015), these practices help them manage their emotional reactions to stressful situations. A proactive attitude to emotional well-being is reflected in recognizing problems as opportunities. Research by Ansong et al. (2023) demonstrates how Filipino students use constructive strategies to sustain resilience, especially in the face of difficult situations.

Additionally, Plaza (2023) emphasizes that coping strategies affect students' emotional health. According to the study by Sun X et al. (2023), using social media for relaxation and positive reinforcement also involves an adaptation of emotion-focused coping aimed at preventing academic burnout. Furthermore, the high level of problem-focused coping suggests that these students are actively seeking “answers” to the pressures they face to control their emotions. This is consistent with the paradigm proposed by Lazarus and Folkman (1984), which suggests that people use problem-focused coping when they believe they can change the stressful situation. The students' tendency to use resources like libraries and the internet, brainstorm solutions, and ask friends and family for help shows that they are actively addressing their problems. As highlighted by Karahalil et al. (2025), who discovered that simulation-based training is essential for bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, this proactive approach helps make situations manageable through practice and reduces anxiety about future responsibilities. According to Freire et al. (2020), to adapt flexibly to different stressors, effective coping often involves a combination of problem-solving and emotion regulation. Research consistently demonstrates a favorable association between adaptive coping skills and improved academic achievement and school adjustment; the overall high level of coping strategies seen is encouraging (Shan & Xu, 2025). Adaptable students are more likely to stay involved, endure, and succeed academically, according to Garcia Perez et al. (2025). As a result, these maritime students' strong coping strategies are an important asset that will help them deal with the demands of their academic program and future professions.

Level of Students' Academic Attitudes

Table 2 presents the level of students' academic attitudes. The overall mean score obtained is 4.03 with a standard deviation of 0.58, which is described as high. This means that students generally maintain a positive and favorable attitude toward their academic environment. When examined by indicator, attitude towards teachers obtained the highest mean of 4.08, suggesting that students particularly value and respect

the role their teachers play in their learning experience. Attitude towards how classes are handled followed closely with a mean of 4.06, reflecting that students are satisfied and engaged with the way their classes are conducted. Lastly, attitude towards other students garnered a mean of 3.95, indicating that students generally get along well with their classmates and feel a sense of belongingness in their academic environment. The relatively low standard deviation further indicates that the responses of the students were consistent with one another, suggesting that the high level of academic attitudes is observed across the entire group of respondents.

Table 2. *Level of Academic Attitudes*

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Attitude towards teacher	0.64	4.08	High
Attitude towards other students	0.69	3.95	High
Attitude towards how classes are handled	0.58	4.03	High
Total	0.58	4.03	High

The study's results show that maritime students at DMMA College generally have strong coping skills, effectively handling academic stress and challenges. The results suggest that most students can adjust to the demands of their studies by managing their time, seeking help when needed, and keeping a positive mindset (Binková & Štěpánková, 2025). Academic resilience is a psychological mechanism that enables students to turn stressful situations into opportunities for growth (Mulati & Purwandari, 2022). This reflects how specialized training environments help students become more disciplined and resilient over time by developing the personal ability to endure stress (Widianti, 2023). In academic attitudes, the overall mean of 4.03 (SD = 0.58) indicates that students have a positive outlook toward their studies. Students view their teachers favorably, especially for their subject knowledge, as this helps build trust and motivation in the classroom (Mudakir et al., 2024). Students also get along well with their classmates, creating a supportive learning environment, socialization, and shared goals (Torii et al., 2023). In addition, students enjoy interactive and hands-on activities, which shows that they learn better through experiential learning processes (Abeysiriwardhane, 2020). The findings also show that the remaining students who are better at handling stress tend to adopt a more positive, motivated approach to their studies (Estrada-Araoz et al., 2024). Coping practices, such as problem-solving and seeking support, are strongly associated with higher levels of academic engagement (Vizoso, C., 2018). When students possess self-efficacy and active coping skills, they are more likely to perceive academic challenges as manageable (Freire et al., 2020). Furthermore, the results suggest that coping practices can actually influence students' academic attitudes. Because it shows how students deal with stress can directly enhance their academic satisfaction and overall well-being (Barbé et al., 2025). Implementing stress management modules within the curriculum can help students develop the flexibility needed for success (Binková & Štěpánková, 2025). Overall, the study highlights the importance of students practicing coping and deep learning in a realistic environment (Jamil & Bhuiyan, 2021).

Correlation Between Measures

Table 3 shows the relationship between coping practices and academic attitudes. The data met the assumptions for Pearson's correlation, as both the IV and DV were continuous and approximately normally distributed (Shapiro-Wilk: $p > 0.05$). It has a ($p=.000$), rejecting the null hypothesis. There is a relationship between coping practices and academic attitudes. An r -value of .536 indicates a moderate relationship. Better coping practices mean better academic attitudes.

Table 3. *Relationship between Coping Practices and Academic Attitudes*

	r	p	Decision	Interpretation
Coping Practices and Academic Attitudes	.536	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant

Note: Significant at $p < .01$

The findings in Table 3 suggest that students who use coping practices are likely to develop good academic attitudes. Coping practices like emotional regulation, problem-solving, social support-seeking, and stress management play a crucial role in how students perceive and respond to academic demands. When students have effective coping strategies, they are better at managing stress, which helps them feel more motivated in their studies. Struthers, Perry, and Menec (2000) found that students who use coping practices report being more motivated to engage in their schoolwork than those who are overwhelmed by academic challenges. Similarly, Robotham (2008) noted that students who manage school stress show a positive view toward their studies, which reinforces their idea that coping practices directly shape academic attitudes. Furthermore, Gustems-Carnicer and Calderón (2013) emphasized that coping practices significantly influence students' view of themselves as learners and their overall attitude toward studying. Students who develop coping mechanisms, such as avoidance or denial, often adopt academic attitudes that can hinder their performance. Overall, the moderate positive correlation observed in this study ($r = .536$, $p < .01$) aligns with the broader body of literature, affirming that coping practices are a significant contributor to the formation of academic attitudes among students. These findings highlight the importance of integrating coping skills development into academic support programs to help students cultivate healthier attitudes toward learning and improve their overall academic well-being.

Regression Analysis of Coping practices and Academic attitudes

The data satisfied the assumptions of multiple linear regression, with linearity confirmed via significant $F(2, 334) = 67.487$, independence of observations assumed given the cross-sectional design, homoscedasticity supported by normally distributed residuals, no multicollinearity concern as the two predictors were entered simultaneously, and normality of the regression model supported by $R = .536$ and $R^2 = .288$. Emotion-focused and problem-focused coping practices have p-values below the .05 level of significance; hence, both subscales influence academic attitudes. Of the two sub-scales, problem-focused is a stronger predictor than emotion-focused (beta values of 0.292 versus 0.215).

Table 4. *Domains of Coping Practices Influencing Academic Attitudes*

	B	P	Decision	Interpretation
(Constant)	2.043	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Emotion-focused	0.215	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Problem-focused	0.292	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant

Note: Model fit at $p = .000$; $r = .538$; $r^2 = .288$

Table 4 presents the regression analysis examining the domains of coping practices that influence academic attitudes. The data satisfied the assumptions of multiple linear regression, with linearity confirmed via significant $F(2, 334) = 67.487$, independence of observations assumed given the cross-sectional design, homoscedasticity supported by normally distributed residuals, no multicollinearity concern as the two predictors were entered simultaneously, and normality of the regression model supported by $R = .536$ and $R^2 = .288$. The results reveal that both emotion-focused and problem-focused coping significantly influence students' academic attitudes, with both subscales yielding p-values of .000, which are below the .05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected for both predictors, indicating that each coping domain significantly contributes to academic attitudes. Of the two subscales, problem-focused coping emerged as the stronger predictor ($\beta = 0.292$) compared to emotion-focused coping ($\beta = 0.215$). Furthermore, the R^2 value of .288 indicates that approximately 28.8% of the variance in academic attitudes is explained by the two coping-practice domains combined. These findings suggest that

students who manage their emotions and actively solve problems are meaningful contributors to shaping their academic attitudes. Problem-focused coping involves directly addressing the source of stress through planning, goal-setting, and active problem-solving. This appears to have a stronger influence on academic attitudes. Struthers, Perry, and Menec (2000) emphasized that students who engaged in active, problem-oriented coping strategies demonstrate higher academic motivation and more positive attitudes toward their studies. This coping practice helps students manage the emotional distress associated with academic pressures, enabling them to maintain a balanced outlook on their learning. Gustems-Carnicer and Calderón (2013) supported this notion, finding that students who effectively regulated their emotions through coping strategies reported better psychological well-being and more favorable academic attitudes. When students are able to manage negative emotions such as anxiety, frustration, and self-doubt, they are better positioned to engage positively with their academic responsibilities.

CONCLUSION

The researchers' findings indicate that BSMT students at DMMA College of Southern Philippines demonstrate a high level of coping, consistently employing both emotion-focused and problem-focused strategies. This means that students have a strong capacity to manage academic stress and challenges. Additionally, students exhibit strong academic attitudes, particularly toward their teachers, classmates, and the organization of their classes, indicating a generally positive perception of their academic environment. There is a significant moderate positive relationship between coping practices and academic attitudes ($r = .536, p < .01$), indicating that students who employ more effective coping strategies tend to maintain more positive academic attitudes. Both problem-focused coping ($\beta = 0.292$) and emotion-focused coping ($\beta = 0.215$) are significant predictors of academic attitudes, with problem-focused coping serving as the stronger predictor. Together, these coping strategies account for 28.8% of the variance in academic attitudes.

Recommendations

1. Students should take time to discover what coping strategies work best for them. Whether it is talking to a friend, praying, taking a break, or making a plan, finding healthy ways to handle stress makes a big difference in handling unexpected situations.
2. Students should make an effort to stay engaged in class, build good relationships with their teachers, and get along well with their classmates. Because a positive attitude toward school makes learning more enjoyable.
3. A teacher being approachable, fair, and genuinely interested in students' progress can keep students motivated and engaged in their studies.
4. The school should create programs that support students' mental health and well-being, such as counseling services and stress management workshops, as these directly affect how students cope and how they feel about their academics.
5. Those in charge of shaping maritime education policies should recognize that students' well-being is just as important as technical training. Incorporating mental health and coping support into institutional standards would greatly benefit maritime students nationwide.
6. Future researchers may want to examine other factors that affect academic attitudes, use larger and more diverse samples, and delve deeper into the topic through interviews and personal accounts to gain a fuller picture of students' experiences in their responses to academics.

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